

Günther Anders' Pathology of Freedom.
Essay on non-identification.

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In a former analysis¹ of the situation of the world, Anders concluded that all animals such as migration birds, know the south by instinct, and the material world they belong to which is necessary for their survival.

But Man cannot foresee his world, he can only know it formally, above its materiality he can only know it "*après coup*", *a posteriori*, and for that, experience is required. His relationship to any determination of the world, is weak because he is expecting anything within the reign of possibility, therefore, no (material) world can be imposed on him, he rather transforms or builds it altogether, applying countless historic variables, as a 'superstructure', or "second world". As a paradoxical expression, we could say, *artificiality is man's nature and inconsistency his essence*.

Man's practical abilities as well as his theoretical constructions account for his abstractive capacity. He is not only part of the (given) world (referred to as '*materialism*'), he is out of it: 'he is not of *this* world'. Abstraction or –freedom from the world- is being carved for what is general, and thus, could be 'anything', the capacity to withdraw from the world, his ability for praxis and transformation, is the fundamental anthropological category. It is the main metaphysical condition of man as well as his *λογος*. his productivity, his interiority, his free will, his historicity² are the coordinates of Anders' matrix.

Man tests his freedom in each and every act towards the world, but the most explicit one is the withdrawal into oneself, by which, he assumes such separation from the world, intensifying and focusing his being to the point of making this openness a real and profound one, he compensates³ the world (or fills in the gap) with his own self, the materialization of the choices made by his free will.

The rest, of his life, follows such experience as its branches⁴, in an unhappy consciousness.

At first this consciousness, is described as nihilistic, sometimes free and others not; sometimes of this world, others 'from another world' *ergo*, lacking self-identification. Such non-identification, is patent in the nihilistic moods experienced by the subject.

To answer this acute anthropological inquiry: to know what man, in a general approach, can be, may be answered with Anders' conceptual matrix.

¹ "*Une Interpretation de l'a posteriori*", *Recherches Philosophiques*, IV, p. 65-80.

² *These concepts, their relationship and leaps among them are important in Anders thought.*

³ *This "gap" is the field of freedom.*

⁴ '*Unhappy consciousness*' in Hegel's terms. Always searching, never satisfied.

HELL: NIHILISTIC PORTRAIT -coming down-

First Circle.

Contingency Shock: "I am precisely myself". The identification of the self with HIS failure.

For Anders, sole capacity of making abstraction of the world, that is, to withdraw from the (external) world accounts sufficiently for the fact of freedom, in other words, the paradoxical fact that Man discovers himself through freedom, by an action that originates freely from himself, he discovers himself as not-free: not determined by himself nor by the world.

These double aspect,

a) Man finds himself in a state of freedom as "existing there beforehand, abandoned, condemned", not constituted by himself with a real irrevocable foundation, as part of the world a priori to him (as a sort of time unfoldment) that defies any succeeding free acts. This irrevocability is absolutely and essentially indeterminate.

Men experience itself as contingent, 'as anybody', as 'precisely me', a self who has not chosen himself as being exactly as he is, but could be entirely different, coming from an origin he cannot tell about and with which, nevertheless, he ought to identify himself 'here' and 'now'. This is the fundamental paradox and reciprocal relationship between freedom and contingency. This paradox is a counterfeit, the fatal gift of freedom is disentangled: Being free means to be foreign; not to be made for particularly anything; to be in any horizon; in an attitude where 'anybody' can be found among other nobodies; In that 'anything', where I can find the reason of my freedom, that is, I find myself, which although being of the world, is still foreign to it. To experience itself as contingent, the self is a victim of his own freedom. Therefore, the notion of contingency has two sides:

- a. the lack of ground of the self by itself
- b. its existence precisely as it is.

Second Circle.

The formulation of the contingency shock: I AM MYSELF, and its forgery.

The translation of this shock: "that I am precisely myself", has been posed in interrogative terms along the history of philosophy, that is, at a theoretical level. For Anders' this is a forgery. The real shock can only be stated with an anacoluthon derivative⁵ because it is so fundamental and too absurd to be answered. The situation worsens if it is stated as a judgement or negative proposition, because the statement has no grounds. The non-problematic theoretical view of this shock is unmasked by facing its underlying foundation: I am –unfortunately- despite everything, nevertheless, myself.

Deceptively, translated as: I AM MYSELF.

The intention of exploring the issue with a dialectic approach sets the verb "is" as a transformation of one determination to another by an ambiguous transition, for Anders, this is out of the question, because what for the logics of dialectic is an equivocal transition is the core of his analysis.

⁵ Mental merengue.

Third Circle.

Extension of the matter of Contingency.

The contingency that the self discovers in himself may not decrease when he relates to the world.

Even though he might get lost most of the time IN the world,

- a. up to the point that the internal division of this contingent and the free self, ceases to be an element of consciousness, neutralizing it.
- b. on the opposite, this relationship with the world and the encounter with any sort of thing, can continuously keep the self in a state of uncertainty `being precisely myself`.

The awe over contingency formulated before in the statement "I am myself", discovers now in each thing and in each place an opportunity to manifest and nourish expressing itself as: "I am not this nor that, but precisely myself"⁶.

The possibility to be anything does not mean, therefore, the unity or kinship of the self, the man nor the world, but on the contrary their total strangeness: *the self can be anything, because he is so strange and so contingent of himself as of every other part of the world.* Every contingent thing which I am not, increases, -now and again- the weight of the fact of being –precisely- what I am.

The world and the self, complement and intensify each other in what they have chance. If the contingent self takes advantage of the world to confirm its own contingency, the world's contingency will be, at the same time, more radical.

From this point forward, the randomness of the identification and the uselessness of self-identification will be attributed to each fragment of the world as such, out of the human contingency, that is, he who is in awe states, "that which is out there, is out there, and nothing else". This state of awe would be, in a sense, in the scope of validity of the non-contradiction principle, and the pathology of this awe is that it continually destroys such frameworks, however, this ends up to the fact that every *hoc et illud* is exactly the same⁷. Each determinate relationship supposes –for the self- the loss of every other possible relationship, *ergo*, every self represents the loss of every other self that he could conform. The awe, limitless, from this point on, is manifested in these expressions and in the shudder of the simple existence of being, has undoubtedly its ultimate foundation in the state of things: Men are basically not carved to be any existent, but to be his own self by himself, to the extent that he becomes part of the world. Nevertheless, he reaches the maximum of the pathological as he remains in the purely theoretical scope, and won't exert his freedom practically in the constitution of his world⁸.

⁶ Relating Holderlin's Empedocles.

⁷ It is not by chance that this ridicule and strangeness are constantly represented in pictorial art, such as still life or the chairs and shoes of the first Van Gogh.

⁸ This is true for all the expressions of freedom discussed here, which belong to those described by Kant, where reason gets confused, instead of becoming practical it rests theoretical. Such antinomies unsolvable in the theoretical scope, are solved by the practical reason, or better still, will never be raised.

Fourth Circle.

Excursus over the general validity of the Philosophic Anthropology statements.

These previous formulations about the non-identification of man with himself are exaggerated, the invoked principle grounds the fact, it seems to be more radical than reality is, which appears pathologic.

If Man continually stopped over the impossibility of self-identification, he would, simply put, be thrown to suicide –as the stoics saw-; there is no other way to elude what one is under the no-freedom state to cancel contingency. However, philosophic exaggeration is no falsification, if the consciousness of contingency is always less precise and more delusive of what general formulae tend to express, these come from the same nihilistic origin and should be redirected to that same nihilist scope. These are not general statements referred to paradox but expressions born from life itself. Exaggeration comes from:

- a) this statements are expressed only exceptional situations
- b) some formulations end and require affective states that lead them at once, to its effective truth.

The exaggeration led to its extreme acuteness, and to a bare truth is

1. In the first place, the situation of contingency itself.
2. In second place, only the statement of its object.

Ergo, the formulae are not only expression of *this* (concrete) existence, but also they inform it, in such a way, that they become truth *in* it.

Even though considered rare, non-identification situations, are not likely (its plausibility is logically compromised) because they are the starting point of nothing, and from the social point of view they only reveal awe or astonishment, as if they are still not-yet. In spite this all, their philosophic value and the use for philosophic anthropology is not undermined. Philosophy tends to consider not philosophic that which is not frequent many times because of the rough and fatal identification with the general and essential, or due to the fact, that only what is verifiable is admitted as a scientific criterion⁹.

It can be sustained, that the rarest human situations, that in the less familiar human types, can perform an interpretative role towards the general, under the sole consideration of its rarity as a fact.

And so, it must be said that a state of shock of the contingent is extremely rare because:

- a) In the first place, the duplicity of the self is not praxis-experienced: man can really (truthfully) make something of himself which afterwards is found as preexistent;
- b) In second place, because the mortal shock is solved in attitudes considered as a *modus vivendi*, attitudes which hide its contingency¹⁰.

Ergo, it is the fact of variation, and not the constant of variability what defines the specifically human in philosophical anthropology.

⁹ It is noteworthy in this state of things that K. Jaspers treated his 'limit-situations' which are clearly rare, in a Psychology of Worldviews.

¹⁰Man is "general" in a very special way, he is not accomplished according to a foreseen and valid form in general, but as history and daily life show, following countless typologies.

As a counter example, the nihilist who perpetuates the inconsistency and indetermination of his role, who cannot decide on any determination and confuses “can” with the conditional “could” that only wishes to encounter with his most “formal” self, is an exceptional case. We will undoubtedly introduce henceforth, a relevant type of man as the true subject of philosophic anthropology.

Fifth Circle.

Shame as conscious reality: a classic of concealment.

The state of shock as a life’s attitude, far from presumption, is called: shame. It is not the kind of shame derived from actions I have done, even though this also means that I do not identify myself with something originated by me, which nevertheless I should forcibly would have to identify with. The mere fact of experiencing such particular shame, demands as a formal condition that I am capable, at the same time, to be identical and not identical with myself; to get out of my skin and think of it differently as myself (category of strangeness); that I can find myself experiencing freedom but –not being free-. Shame is not born from this incoherence (which is a consequence), it is originally unravel¹¹. In shame, the self pretends to free himself to the extent that he feels definitely abandoned, but everywhere he runs he remains irrevocably in the impasse, at the mercy of himself. This is how he experiences “not put by myself” and therefore, feels for the first time that he comes from somewhere that is not himself, he senses the past. Not the familiar or historic past but the alien, irrevocable, transcendent origin: man senses the world he comes from but does not belong to as self. Therefore, shame is shame of the origin. Even though, this origin appears as, that which is not, while free: that which cannot be chosen freely, it is a characteristic human category. Animals have not leaped from the origin to freedom, only Man can maintain the bond to what he comes from. What starts as shame ends as honor: He who feels shames returns to himself. To be able to do this: do not stay adrift at the mercy of the world, to link the heritage of “being precisely myself, and also “be of the world” and come back to one’s self is the testimony of man’s double condition: even though he is different from himself, nevertheless is his very self. When he is ashamed he flees to himself. He wants to be swallowed in the dirt, but can only intern in himself (proud to escape) until he can forget the reason of his flight (not being himself).

The ashamed is proud of his hiding, he sublimates his shame and falsifies his true motive which was the scandal of shame, of the identification failure. He turns shame into a virtue. The concealment mends the hidden by its secrecy, or better still, it keeps it as his most intimate and implicit self: that which belongs to me and only to myself. This concealment appropriates of what is hidden, of what the world is, what is “common” with the world, in such a way that is now private and own. These hidden motives are now the occasion, the consolidation of one’s self, a true reason of pride. The one that transforms shame in this way, commits no longer to the world but only to himself, and abstaining of

¹¹ As unfoldment.

it with resistance and purity, denies the fact that he has come to the world as a contingent being and the imposture of worldliness. ¹²

Because of this moral happy ending, shame is the most characteristic sign of this fact. As life goes on, this antinomy has become a *modus vivendi*, the thousand ways of hypocrisy, disguise, and comedy are a positive example of what shame and disgust negatively prove: man's lack of consistency in relation to himself, his haziness. Only provisionally he may abandon his particular existence, take another form and make himself, the matter and occasion, of multiple personifications.

The provisional is conclusive: among all species, the human one, is most lacking of attributes.

Sixth Circle.

The perfect future; The spirit in escape; Man in subjunctive¹³.

It is in shame, that Man discovers himself abandoned, as a being who was there before he experienced himself.

The imperfect tense "I was there" is in a way a sort of denial of me as a free being; and even more, the past perfect tense to which it can be further traced, indicates "that which was there" is not me.

This freedom, that doubts to continue all the way to the past perfect scope, pretending to reach what is below itself, acquires the possibility –for man- to attain a perfect future. This possibility is a sign of his freedom and his non-freedom .

That the future falls in the dimension of the indeterminate, dimension which I can take advantage of, is common place. That philosophies from Hegel to Heidegger, come from Kant's theory of time is no surprise either.

The core is, that if man does not realize this freedom practically, using the dimension of future to go over his contingent `being-precisely-now'¹⁴, if he saves the needed energy at this crucial moment, he consumes his time with his hands tied¹⁵, and commits to the indefinite *ad infinitum*, he compromises his freedom in vain. The more he moves, abandoning his bonds in the direction this so-called freedom unveils, the more he gets lost in the indeterminate reign.

This dragged future, which has qualitatively changed, has dialectically been transformed, suddenly, ceases to be man's future. He is lost in something he can no longer engage to; For this moment/tense, time's specific direction is no longer adequate; In a positive sense, it is reduced to something that is not his future any more: an *αιωv*¹⁶, irrelevant, ungraspable, to the self.

¹² Consciousness' steps to moral alchemy.

¹³ Kind reminder: Present subjunctive can be better defined as **a grammatical mood rather than a proper tense** and is used to express personal opinions, unreal or hypothetical wishes, doubts, commands or feelings in the present or the future.

¹⁴ *Gerade-jezt-Sein*.

¹⁵ In fact, his head

¹⁶ Eternity ["The white hole of eternity within Man"]

Man can still think about the existence of this *αιων*, but in a sterile way, not understanding nor performing it, too far away from his personal and intimate horizon.

The “I will be” is from now on transformed in “what will be, I won’t be”; its correct positive expression in the future perfect tense is: I will have been.

The statement I will have been, points out that man can outlive himself in thought (out-think himself?) which is a remarkable act of freedom and of abstraction.

In the anticipative memory, he comes back to himself as if he was not imprisoned in the framework of his actual life, as if he could live his life beforehand, to go beyond it and preserve his memory, a memory he can go to, but, in a moment of his present life *for which the future is already neutral*.

This freedom to overcome one’s self, of which the perfect future is triumph as it is failure, has its perfect match in the freedom of motion where and how to move freely in space.

As I could have been here, there, and further, anywhere really, the original sense of spatial freedom is transformed in “precisely here” which turns it unbearable due to its contingency. No here is better than other. Running from one subjunctive to another. The original sense of spatial freedom which is the capacity to move from a determinate here to a determinate there is neutralized by the fact that the freedom to move mistakes its way, this neutralization can be expressed as inertia or spirit to escape. We become sick of excessive spaces, seeking only to end this determination carousel gripped by vertigo.

Both, time and space neutralizations, can be identified as the nihilist panic in the freedom paradox: “never wanting to be precisely me, and nevertheless “having to be precisely myself” perpetually. He is the permanent constant in change and time, but can never come back to his real self, because no matter which direction is taken he stays always in a `here´ in the same limitless world, therefore, his terror becomes stupefying.

Determination delimits the self. Man, can come out of his element, that with which he habitually relates to; He may abandon `his´ place and by losing, tries to forget his individuality and belongings, and so, losing what is his, he loses himself.

Seventh Circle.

Thirst for power and desire of Glory.

The self, sick of time, wants to neutralize the contingency of the place where he concretely is. He wants to be everywhere, simultaneously, to seize it all at once. But the desire of possession is only the specification of a deep thirst for power: the wish to make the world congruent with himself, more exactly constrain the world into myself. That the world, at its full extent, can become mine, instead of becoming I, is the first scandal and the first objective for the thirst for power. Even though the thirst of power is a symptom of the contingency shock state, the self, strives as well, to neutralize the fact of contingency. In those situations, in which man is given to himself in anticipation, in which he can only discover and not reinvent himself, and in those situations where the world and the others precede him, his weakness outcrops and is constantly reproached: he cannot stand that

the world stays the same, it is the expression of absolute deception: It is the echo of Nietzsche's aphorism: "If God existed how could I bear not being him?"

In his thirst for power, Man is in search of the advantage that the world has over him, because he is not everything, then from here on he must *have* everything: appropriating and representing it; and being everywhere, omnipresent.

He wishes to be now and forever, to immortalize in time, such as he was busy glorifying himself in space; pretending to deny the contingency of the now to which he is relinquished: His self in the form of a permanent statue. His actual and incomplete state can be seen, as the *phenomenon* in regard, to the *idea*. To this glorious statue, he is only a true and temporary copy, and here lies the paradox: the more his glory increases, the less related is the statue to "himself". The statue has usurped his name and will get the glory in his stead for a long time, even after his death. Overwhelmed and despondent, he remains envious of its big name.

The "Pathology of Freedom", with philosophic exaggerations as a method, describes different ailments of this disease. These pathologies represent radical dangers for men of our time, we all know them, even more than we like to, here we have taken them to catastrophic off limits, compromising life itself. The forms of shame, disgust, desire of glory are familiar to all if we do not habitually discern its contingency it is because they appear ambivalent, masked with positive aspects, they shelter the threat of the contingent, and could lead to suicidal, *modi vivendi*. Shame, disgust and the desire of glory take place in contingent life, therefore, as practical life is an affirmation of the self, they represent commitments to a life woven in contingency, they represent protests and insults, the dark side we all share, because antinomies are not stronger than the love for life. Nihilists also want to live.

ANTHITHESIS: HISTORIC PORTRAIT

-coming up-

Sixth Circle Up.

Life goes on. The contingency shock repeats reluctantly.

The man who constantly and uselessly gets lost in the *impasse* of his own contingency and finds his "being precisely me" as if he had no life behind him, and as if he was reborn every time, carries on with his life, anyway.

That is, the paradox does not arise in an imaginary starting point "before" life, but rather in the middle of life itself, life that goes on regardless and under it, as far as man does not take it as a pretext to end his life. Beyond his fanatic formalism, man recognizes the possibility of a life that perseveres despite of him, and he surrenders to it.

The possibility: of being repeated leads the paradox *ad absurdum*, being a paradox itself, it counterfeits its destructive nature at the same time. In other words, the condition of paradox is iteration, which nests another paradox: which is that should not be repeated inside the life it questions, if it intends a positive outcome.

That is, from a temporal point of view, paradox is neutral, it repeats itself, it is life itself that takes place in time, against all odds, life happens against the paradoxical resistance that opposes its course in every step of its flow, paradox is experienced as an obstacle. It is not the paradox itself that is repeated but life that makes us re-experience the paradoxical, and it is above its outcome that life goes on: it is felt as a specific negation of life during a time lapse.

As iteration of the identical, “movement opposed to memory”¹⁷, iteration is the beginning of the neutralization of historic time inside a life that can -even out of history- follow its course.

This means, that the nihilistic paradox of the experience of freedom, is the characteristic of non-historic existence, more exactly, of the counter-historic existence. By this experience it increases its own difficulty and tries with obstinacy to attack the antinomy's walls that constrains it, and even deprives itself of time, the only thing, that could be historic, and could account for an answer to the paradox. Since then, Man, deeply committed with the idea of antinomy, turns non-historic. That is, what he is and what he was, does not represent strictly a life; deep down, it is nothing but an event that happens by accident; that in relation to the constancy of paradox rests in the scope of the possible so, it cannot be remembered.

The contingency shock destroys then, the strict possibility of experience itself, the fact of appropriating the life lived *de facto*. It all looks as if life had happened “for nothing” the act itself of having been lived, is continually disowned by the paradox. If Man now is exposed to the accidental change of his fortuitous experiences and wants to try to return to himself, he will not be able to reach his life ‘in concrete’, because he really, does not have it. Nevertheless, the paradox becomes more acute because

- a) The paradox is denied as life goes on, and
- b) life is denied by the paradox because it is unfit to remember

(It has pulled the self out of time).

Life has yielded its force and reality to the paradox and elapses as if it was not there. That both, life and paradox are at the same time, -winner and loser- is contradictory only in appearance. If life only continues it is defeated, as paradox is beaten too, but because it is forced to be repeated, it is forced to try to win. If the balance of indifference is not reached, this ambiguity maintains the paradox “alive”; and the lapse lived in life, regardless the paradox determines its pride. In such a way that man in desperation, clings finally to himself and to the contingent fact “to be precisely myself”.

The self, is determined by means of the paradox. So, if we think of a new type of man – the historic man- we cannot picture him as a contingent shock fugitive, he must be considered as a *sui generis* type who is beyond the contingency shock and whose main features, such as memory and the ability to experience, do not represent subsequent acts towards salvation, but originally *modi vivendi*.

¹⁷ Kierkegaard, t. III, 5, p. 171.

Fifth Circle Up.

“I remember *ergo*, I am” as the minimum identification.

The nihilist expresses himself in the proposition “I am precisely myself”, when he wants to escape from himself, goes around in circles, or simply encounters a complete contingent stranger that carries his name. This proposition expresses, deep down, his indignation for the fact that parts of his being do not match, in accordance to, some miraculous preset harmony. He is not aware that such identity may be established with memories afterwards, which can be proved by a sort of Cartesian argumentation. From the memory’s perspective, the antinomy and the identification difficulties just described are not visible.

Because what I find in my memory, as myself, contains not only “the stranger”, but precisely the I: the whole subject. Yesterday’s man that I remember contains both I(s) in an unsolvable unity.

This same man who astonishes today of his contingency, has the possibility of remembering being astonished yesterday for that same reason.

In this way, a minimum of identification is accomplished in a Cartesian style.

The self insists no more in his being-here, nor in his being-now, he has suddenly discovered a determination of himself (in yesterday’s contingency thought) with which he can consciously identify himself today: Both united in the memory. The object of the memory is already an identity: “The one that I was, I am” and “I remember *ergo*, I am myself”.

In these both memory’s I(s) intersect:

- a) Yesterday’s I -the formal one- and the contingent I, could be confused:
- b) In yesterday’s I everything that happened is blurry and confused.
- c) Yesterday’s I is not an I, it is a fragment of life, to the eyes of today’s memory.

Fourth Circle.

Identification and Possessive.

What does one remember? For philosophical anthropology, is a decisive question.

Unlike perception which has its object in front: a fragment of the world, the memory is about a situation in which the one who perceives and what is perceived, the I and the world, are fused to the point that neither can be separated of this single element.

Vgr. If I see a misfortune coming it is still strange (away of myself). It fills me with anguish: which is nothing but stupefaction of the self at a radically foreign object. Non the less, as a memory, the misfortune is already mine. Not only the memory of its coming, and my subjective reaction but the whole situation that includes both aspects; It appears as a fragment of life. Taking into account this fragment of life, it is simply impossible to befall in the astonishment that “I myself have to be myself” as in the case of painful experiences, it is not the self who evokes the memory and arranges what is remembered, but the memory itself warns the self and arranges him. In identical situations, it is not the self who defines itself, but the lived experience. This way, the self is not as indeterminate as it was before. From this point of view, the contingency shock, never mind the terror that goes with is a sort of additional element: the horror of “being precisely myself”

disappears because of the truly unpleasant memory, which can be taken to a previous time, seems futile.

The memories of contingent events that one has lived, the ones that have accidentally happened, are fused with the self.

The identity is established before the terror of the identification is manifested.

Important conclusions for the notion of experience can be drawn:

- a) The memory nullifies indetermination and contingency.
- b) In memory Man discovers himself as situation not as self: what he experienced before now *he is*; and if he could make abstraction of his being-so (*sosein*), of all he has experienced, and the modes of all his history, he would be left with nothing, not even his *afore being*.. So life is the field of particular experiences, where each and every one of them is mine and I call upon, anytime. Man through his history, which forms and surrounds him, escapes from strangeness and from the contingency of "being precisely himself".

The identical proposition "I am myself", analytic in its origin but denied by the contingent shock, is transformed to this more meaningful one: "I am my life" or "the self is life". It transforms in an identity proposition, truly synthetic: the **I** and the **is** or **am** of both are exchangeable: life not only embodies the first or third person (something strange and contingent), it is also a possessive: it is mine, it is my life. This "mine" does not point to the I as the owner of the life that belongs to him.

The possessive pronoun, in general does not refer only to the one who possess but also to what is possessed; the neutral refers to the general fact of belonging. "My" life means, then, that I belong to my life as much as my life belongs to me.

The most diverse features of the historic man, give testimony of his identity, which memory reveals under its formal aspect. The historic man would see as absurd and nihilistic notions about transcendence and/or earthly being-here created out of the self. He is beyond the past/present polarity. He has his own past, which is linked not only with his experience but to other beings and persons. Just as the time of his ancestors is not really alien to him, just far.

Third Circle Up.

What is called "I", from tomorrow on will be called "Life". The formal I.

If the I brings back to his life, through memories, his original contingency and *a posteriori* experiences, this after identification does not represent any identification nor organization of the matter of life because the I is formal from now on. Because this I is the vanguard of the material life's plenitude. If the I is formal, it is thanks to life; It is because life, willing and bound to consider all possibilities, to experience the new, and prove the presence of the spirit, is formalized in the I and culminates in an acute and lucid present, in such a way that it puts an end to life's material richness to step into another scope: the I is the vanguard of the condition to be "Man". In order to integrate -experience and world- into life, what today is I, from tomorrow on, is my life pulled together with everything that comes up, and a part of what my life is today was yesterday's "I".

The alternative of the I, and the contingent determination that left the nihilist in constant shock, was somehow a misunderstanding of the I and its own role; he

pointed out his conditioned formality and his presence as freedom, as opposed to life “which was simply material” and is sunk in the past. This misunderstanding about himself, which in the counter-historic case, leads the I to break with life, but does not happen to the historic man.

The conception of the I as a constituent element of life, (as a moment, in a logic and temporal sense) shall not be understood as if there were no difference between both forms of life of the I (nihilistic and historic). These are, one and the same in the memory, nevertheless memory itself is not a difference, but a perpetual identification. A certain duality is obvious. A sort of gap, that life risks between herself and the I, because when it conforms the I, it is not the moment in which it outdistances in the freedom of its possibilities or when it wants to be updated. This gap always disappears in the memory, and identity is reestablished.

This befall of the I in its life does not happen at once. The I surrenders to life’s force of attraction, and is pulled into the core of life in such a way that it disappears as an I and as terminal point of the present. Life and I are melted together as only the possessive pronoun can describe. The life that is thus found in remembrance, needs not anymore of particular distinctions or actualizations of past situations, nor exact repetitions of past experiences, -ambiance and feelings suffice- from which images or actualizations may be revived as a subsequent process¹⁸.

Second Circle Up.

Identification in stable situations.

The exposition of the identity and identification problem shall address at least one situation in which the panic of identity does not happen and the problem of identification does not arise.

To find himself, Man needs to overlap the artificial over the natural world, that is, the social and economic world built by him with its ways and laws, which demonstrates that he is not made for this natural world. Nevertheless, this second world, always diverse in historic conditions can stabilize up to the point that man can find himself so comfortable that problems and pathologic attitudes of identity, become secondary, the same way as the identification through history.

Under stable social conditions, it is the world that naturally identifies the I before any auto-identification is needed.

The social world performs a minimal identification as having a name. Once a man is baptized –nobody baptizes himself- the name persists as a constant in life, it is such a natural constant that no one cares for the nominalism-realism debate, no one pretends to be called James or Jane, he IS James or Jane.

But the identification takes place when the environment remains somehow identical and identifiable, because the identification of the I depends on its correlative world.

The role that the name performs, can be so natural and stable that prevents the role-man (teacher, judge, doctor etc.) to think about himself independently as a simple *substratum*, therefore, to conceive himself apart from the role, as an “empty I” that makes possible

¹⁸ Cfr. Proust M. *À la recherche du temps perdu*. C1.

that a man may see no difference nor antinomy between his role and himself and neither restrict his existence to an abstract I.

In stable situations, the role phenomenon “in-what” and “the-what” resembles the is, no less than the I phenomenon.

That the role represents the accident and the I the substratum –valid distinction- for what we now-a-days experience, in the social world which constantly transforms and changes man without ceasing his roles, so many social and historic situations are not considered a priori. In stable or stationary times it is entirely possible that the role has an I, at least that the tension and non-identity described above about in the nihilist portrait does not take place.

The social worldliness¹⁹ will be present from now on, as a role. That the world is nothing “exterior” something added to the I, reveals the futility of the terror of the contingent and the need of interiorizing it through its remembrance and its due assimilation.

We might think then, that no identification is thus required, but this is not the case, because in stable situations, man must adapt and answer to the requirements the world calls for. This correspondence of actions does not refer to the simple memory acts which are the means to historic identification. They are founded mainly in moral ones, above all I responsible acts. Of what I did yesterday, of what I shall do tomorrow and answer to the world about them. This identity manifests not a historic nature but of a legal and moral one. They only become historic, when all the above elements become vague and confused and Man is bound to be called by his name to answer about them with his identity and get back in himself. The same way as the part of the heart “of duty” in Kantian thought, the call for identity looms from the heart of the historic man.

When he answers his own call, and when he uses his own name he encounters and comes back to himself. Seen from a stable situation, the historic man reminds the baron Münchhausen who comes out of a swamp by pulling his own hair up.

From this point of view, identity guaranties the social world, with both types described:

- a) the nihilist (who does not succeed identifying himself) and
- b) the historic (who manages his own identification)

They do not appear, as they did before, so far from each other, as both need identification. And the necessary staging of the rescue of the historic man, as well as the evident catastrophe of the nihilist, both testify its identical position: the strangeness of the world. Nevertheless this similarity, the nihilistic portrait is philosophically more important, than the man situated in the historic existence.

If the essence of man is not fixed, then in his inclination to multiple incarnations, it is the nihilist who makes this inconsistency his definite fate, who determines himself with this indetermination, instead of taking advantage to specify himself one way or the other. The nihilist incarnation of indetermination, is, because of the way he shows his faults without disguise, an exaggerated portrait of man. On the other hand, the portrait of a historic man, seems doubtful simplicity. The historic Man appears as an I who is up to what happens, of his contingency, a man who has the courage to risk his *amor fati*, he follows closely his *fatum* and calls it “myself” always. In Hegel’s terms, he turns a posteriori into “rational” all

¹⁹ *Soziale Weltlichkeit.*

that is contingent in him. He has the courage to say in the face to what happens to him: "this is mine".

Open Field: Earthly Surface.

On philosophic Anthropology.

The identification process is not so simple.

When the self is not identified and situated by the world, he needs to identify himself. Non the less, it is not enough to situate one's self. Without the world, the identification is not possible. Only the one who gets in action, (the one that is capable of abstracting the socially identified self) is out of the difficulties and terrors of contingency, because he does not insist on his past, which he has assimilated, but in his task towards the world.

Even though the world has not given him a determinate place, as he has not done either with the nihilist, the historic self effectively achieves his identity.

To the eyes of whom has a will, what he wants is compared to everything he finds: his empiric existence, something that is not contingent. This which is not contingent, -on the opposite to his experience- does not need to be assimilated; It is the will which shall be assimilated²⁰.

That the world appears contingent to he who wants to modify it is possible, but it is out of all contingency the it is HE who wants, and has the will to transform it.

If we now tried to reinterpret the proposition "that I want precisely this" this last would appear as a mere construction: it is absolutely inconceivable from the will. If this formula was accepted from the situation of the will, it would neutralize the will. This man that wants precisely something may be against the world and even if it has not given him a determinate place, he can, anyway, conquer an effective identification that he would express with a proposition that is not the nihilist's: "I am myself" nor the historic self's: "I am who I was", but would be: "What I wanted, I want". The constant is already in the concept of "task", therefore there is no need for it to be maintained as a memory or experience, because the tasks only disappears once it is accomplished²¹.

By this recourse to action, philosophic anthropology reaches its legitimacy peak, its capacity and competence. From the point of view of what man does, the question "What is, and who is him authentically? Seems erroneously posed, because the action is not the being.

It was Hegel who left this action disappear when he considered it in each case as a development and an outcome (and the action comes to be after, and as past, an actual entity), allowing it to be swallowed in each case by the triad of the being itself, he transforms it anyway is an sort of "being". A type of being not specifically human, which not by chance he called "organic". This tentative, of limitless consequences, now darkens the action phenomena. Non the less it was Kant who addressed the issue openly , even

²⁰ It is not by chance, that many will to will to escape from contingency, because the fact of having a task represents – for them- a solution.

²¹ It is very characteristic to observe that the permanence of the will derives, without the slightest hidden purpose, in the unicity of a life and that few biographies -even autobiographies-, offer such a sharp unity of great men of state or revolutionaries, whose will aim to anything but identity. Unlike to autobiographical experience this unity, thus, turns in a sort of award.

though Hegel formulated more explicitly the issue of self-identification (Hegel characterizes history as the act of the spirit coming back to itself that was not identical to itself). The self-identification through *Aufklärung* and the critic are for Kant an action; For him is not about ascertaining what reason is (which for him is equivalent to Man), but to build it through a critical action.

Against this, Hegel asks himself what reason is, to answer dialectically that it is not the Being (or self) in such a way that even negatively the given answer remains theoretical. He takes the qualitative leap from the theoretical to the practical after the term 'emerge' and repositions it in the theoretical scope.

Kant's objectives are Anders' and have a further reach of what was thought at first. Philosophic anthropology and its problem of the definition of man, should be considered, facing human action, as a productive misunderstanding and should be ended.

The issue of knowing what man authentically is (*eigentlich*) is therefore, formulated mistakenly, because the theoretical definition is only a shadow that decision throws in the field of the theoretical. "What I am in an authentic sense", "What I discover in me", is always decided either by me or by somebody else. What is opposed to the definition of "man" is not, therefore, something irrational, but the fact of human action; Action, effectively, by which man is continuously defined, and determines what he is in each occasion. In this perpetual definition of himself that man offers with his actions, it is useless to appeal to the order principle and demand a short stop to raise the questions of an 'authentic' definition and establish who is man in an 'authentic' sense. There is nothing more suspicious than such 'authenticity' (*Eigenlichkeit*).

It is not by chance that the issue of definition is mostly raised in reactive situations. In particular in uncertainty or crisis states in which it is no longer something precise. The one posing the question is the inactive, the one who compromises the real transformation and poses this problem, in a retroactive way; "Who am I authentically?", he says instead of defining himself effectively and making something of himself. He is, therefore, what himself or any other, with the help of an old practice definition has made of himself.

Consequently, **the question of knowing who am I, is not one of those to be considered but answered.**

To conclude, the issues that philosophic anthropology considered at first in The pathology of human freedom appear as a flaw that denatures the problems. It turns autonomy in a definition of itself, and while it teaches man to run after his "*Eigenlichkeit*", life happens, abandoning him to those who want to indoctrinate and make him lose his freedom.